

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

1. Please, tell me about your history of hearing loss.

How long have you had your hearing loss / been deaf? How many years and months of experience do you have with the devices?

	Time (years, months) and reason
	Hearing loss / Deafness
Left ear: HA <input type="radio"/> CI <input type="radio"/>	
Right ear: HA <input type="radio"/> CI <input type="radio"/>	

How long do you use the devices daily?

	Daily use (hours)
Hearing aid	<input type="radio"/> Full day <input type="radio"/> ____ hours <input type="radio"/> Less than 3 h
Cochlear implant	<input type="radio"/> Full day <input type="radio"/> ____ hours <input type="radio"/> Less than 3 h
Both in combination	<input type="radio"/> Full day <input type="radio"/> ____ hours <input type="radio"/> Less than 3 h

Devices	Manufacturer	Model
Hearing aid		
Cochlear implant		

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

In the following you can give your answer to the questions on the given scales. If you think you cannot give an answer or the question is not applicable in another way, you can check the box "N/A" (not applicable).

2. Can you have a conversation with someone when another person is speaking, whose voice is the same pitch¹ as the person you are talking to?

3. You are sitting in between two people. One of them starts to speak. Can you tell right away whether it is the person on your left or your right, without having to look?

4. Can you tell how far away a bus or a truck is, from the sound?

5. Do everyday sounds that you can hear easily seem clear to you (not blurred)?

6. Do you have to concentrate very much when listening to someone or something?

¹ Pitch: Height of a tone, if you are talking to a male, another male speaker would be in the background and vice versa.

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

7. Imagine a situation where you are having a conversation without any background noise.

7A) Do you feel there is a difference in perception between your ears in regard to how you perceive the sound from a single sound source?

Explanation: When a sound comes from one source, do you perceive two sounds or one?

7B) Do you perceive differences in the following aspects in regard to your devices?

Please, set one cross only. If you perceive the sound higher/stronger with the CI, give a score above zero. Is it higher/stronger with the Hearing aid, give a score below zero. Mark zero if there is no difference.

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how the height of tones is perceived?

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how loudness is perceived?

Is there a device you use more to determine where a sound comes from?

Which device do you prefer in regard to sound quality?

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

8. Imagine a situation where you are having a conversation with a person while other people are talking around you. This could be in a canteen or a busy restaurant.

8A) Do you feel there is a difference in perception between your ears in regard to how you perceive the sound from a single sound source?

Explanation: When a sound comes from one source, do you perceive two sounds or one?

8B) Do you perceive differences in the following aspects in regard to your devices?

Please, set one cross only. If you perceive the sound higher/stronger with the CI, give a score above zero. Is it higher/stronger with the Hearing aid, give a score below zero. Mark zero if there is no difference.

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how loudness is perceived?

Is there a device you use more to determine where a sound comes from?

Which device do you prefer in regard to sound quality?

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

9. Imagine a situation where you are having a conversation with a person in nature, such as when you are in the forest or at the sea, when the wind makes noise.

9A) Do you feel there is a difference in perception between your ears in regard to how you perceive the sound from a single sound source?

Explanation: When a sound comes from one source, do you perceive two sounds or one?

9B) Do you perceive differences in the following aspects in regard to your devices?

Please, set one cross only. If you perceive the sound higher/stronger with the CI, give a score above zero. Is it higher/stronger with the Hearing aid, give a score below zero. Mark zero if there is no difference.

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how the height of tones is perceived?

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how loudness is perceived?

Is there a device you use more to determine where a sound comes from?

Which device do you prefer in regard to sound quality?

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

10. Imagine a situation where you are having a conversation with a person while there is traffic noise present, such as during rush hour.

10A) Do you feel there is a difference in perception between your ears in regard to how you perceive the sound from a single sound source?

Explanation: When a sound comes from one source, do you perceive two sounds or one?

10B) Do you perceive differences in the following aspects in regard to your devices?

Please, set one cross only. If you perceive the sound higher/stronger with the CI, give a score above zero. Is it higher/stronger with the Hearing aid, give a score below zero. Mark zero if there is no difference.

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how the height of tones is perceived?

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how loudness is perceived?

Is there a device you use more to determine where a sound comes from?

Which device do you prefer in regard to sound quality?

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

11. Imagine a situation where you are having a conversation with a person while there is music present, such as in the living room with the radio on.

11A) Do you feel there is a difference in perception between your ears in regard to how you perceive the sound from a single sound source?

Explanation: When a sound comes from one source, do you perceive two sounds or one?

11B) Do you perceive differences in the following aspects in regard to your devices?

Please, set one cross only. If you perceive the sound higher/stronger with the CI, give a score above zero. Is it higher/stronger with the Hearing aid, give a score below zero. Mark zero if there is no difference.

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how the height of tones is perceived?

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how loudness is perceived?

Is there a device you use more to determine where a sound comes from?

Which device do you prefer in regard to sound quality?

Questionnaire for users of a hearing aid and cochlear implant (bimodal listeners)

Niclas A. Janßen, PhD student at DTU's hearing systems group

12. Imagine a situation where you are having a conversation with a person while many sounds are present, such as while shopping in a supermarket.

12A) Do you feel there is a difference in perception between your ears in regard to how you perceive the sound from a single sound source?

Explanation: When a sound comes from one source, do you perceive two sounds or one?

12B) Do you perceive differences in the following aspects in regard to your devices?

Please, set one cross only. If you perceive the sound higher/stronger with the CI, give a score above zero. Is it higher/stronger with the Hearing aid, give a score below zero. Mark zero if there is no difference.

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how the height of tones is perceived?

Is there a difference between your ears in regard to how loudness is perceived?

Is there a device you use more to determine where a sound comes from?

Which device do you prefer in regard to sound quality?

